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IMPROVING THE PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF YOUNG CHILDREN THROUGH THE USE OF NATIONAL GAMES

Qo'shmurodov Bekzod Abduraimovich

JDPU. Faculty of Physical Culture, acting associate professor

Hasanov Anvar Tokhirovich

JDPU. Faculty of Physical Culture, senior teacher

Abstract. *In this article, the problem of raising the physical qualities of children through the national games of the Uzbek people was not completely a subject of special research in the system of physical culture and folk pedagogy. From this point of view, this work is important because it is aimed at solving this problem in a scientific direction.*

Key words: *Folk games, physical qualities, students, pedagogy.*

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКИХ КАЧЕСТВ ДЕТЕЙ МАЛОГО ВОЗРАСТА С ПОМОЩЬЮ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ИГР

Аннотация. *В данной статье проблема воспитания физических качеств детей посредством национальных игр узбекского народа не была полностью предметом специального исследования в системе физической культуры и народной педагогики. С этой точки зрения данная работа важна, поскольку направлена на решение данной проблемы в научном направлении.*

Ключевые слова: *Народные игры, физические качества, студенты, педагогика.*

MILLIY O'INLARIDAN FOYDALANISH ORGALI BOLALARNING JISMONIY SIFATLARINI OSHIRISH

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada o'zbek halq milliy o'yinlari vositasida 9 yosh bolalarning jismoniy sifatlarini tarbiyalash muammosi jismoniy madaniyat tizimida hamda, xalq pedagogikasida to'liq holda maxsus tadqiqod predmeti bo'lgan emas. Shu nuqtai nazardan qaraganda, mazkur ish bu muammoni ilmiy yo'nalishda yechishga qaratilganligi bilan muhimdir.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Xalq o'yinlari, jismoniy sifatlar, o'quvchilar, pedagogika.*

INTRODUCTION

The upbringing of the younger generation in a healthy and harmonious way poses great challenges for physical culture. It creates a need to nationalize physical culture, which allows us to raise the younger generation to be physically strong and develop their physical qualities, and to review the ways and methods of collecting, implementing in life and school, and developing the national games of our people, which are becoming increasingly popular.

Collecting and studying the wealth of creativity created by the Uzbek people for thousands of years, passed down from generation to generation, and educating the younger generation to be spiritually rich, morally pure, and physically harmonious on the basis of these rich treasures is one of the urgent issues of today. Especially after Uzbekistan gained independence, attention to our national values and traditions has increased. This has begun to manifest itself to varying degrees in all aspects of life, including in physical culture, which is one of the main parts of education. "Physical education," it is stated in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Physical Education and Sports", - it is emphasized in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Physical Education and Sports", - is an integral part of the national culture of the peoples of the Republic of Uzbekistan, an important means of physical, cultural, and spiritual development."

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Scientists T. Usmonkhodjaev, Abdullaev U., Abdumalikov R., Abdullaev A., Alabin V.G. and other scientists conducted scientific research.

Much work has been done to study the socio-pedagogical characteristics of folk national games. A number of scientists have discussed in their research to one degree or another the use of folk national games.

Prominent scientists in our republic, engaged in the problems of physical culture, have achieved certain achievements in the field of studying Uzbek folk national games. One of such works is the work of Professor T. Usmonkhodjaev.

RESULTS

The effectiveness of traditional (physical education-based) exercises that do not include research exercises and exercises with these exercises was determined in both groups based on pre-study and post-study testing. In order to study the physical development of secondary school students, the results of preliminary and final tests (60-meter run, 4X10-meter shuttle run, pull-ups on a high horizontal bar, standing long jump) were obtained in the observation and research groups. The analyzed results are given in the tables above.

Based on the above, it was determined that the exercises should be performed from 2-4 to 8-10 times in one series for 5-20 minutes: the rest time between exercises

should be set at 20-30 seconds, and 2-3 series of exercises should be performed, and between series, rest should be 30-40-70-80-100 seconds.

DISCUSSION.

So, if the exercises given according to the physical education program are reduced during the training process and a set of exercises that develop physical qualities, movement and national games are included in the training, the effectiveness of the training will increase even more.

CONCLUSION.

In addition to acyclic exercises, jumping, throwing, and gymnastic exercises are also used during physical education classes of preparatory groups. When standardizing the acyclic physical exercise load, it is necessary to assess the speed of movement and the restoration of physiological processes.

Currently, when assessing the physical exercise load, the energy spent on muscle movements is taken into account more.

When standardizing the acyclic physical exercise load, it is necessary to take into account its pace, intensity, and number of repetitions of the movement, and the results of correction and systematic control aimed at improving the movement should be taken into account.

When standardizing the acyclic physical exercise load, special attention should be paid to the duration of the exercises. In the context of improving movement, the optimal interval ratio at the beginning of exercise series indicates the need to adhere to the optimal pace.

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